

A STUDY ON PROBLEMS FACED BY WORKING WOMEN IN CBSE SCHOOLS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO ERODE DISTRICT

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"When woman moves forward, the family moves, the village moves and the nation moves"

- Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru

She is a symbol of power, she stands out in hundreds, she possesses all the divine virtues and she is considered to be the most beautiful creations of God; She is a Woman!

Abstract:

In olden days man was considered as breadwinner and women was consider as home maker but today everything was changed .Both men and women have equal responsibility in work and family. Women's participation in teaching profession has increased. The increasing trend of women's participation in the teaching profession poses problems. One of these challenges, concerns in balancing their role between family and job responsibility that faced by many women teachers. As we all know that education is crucial in the development of any country. Teacher is the most important component of the education system. Any education system is only as good as the teacher. The main focus of this research is to identify the problems faced by working women in education sector. The major objectives of the study were to find out the real problems of female school teachers, to find out the causes of the problem and to suggest reasonable solution to those problems. The problems of employed women will vary with the nature of job, sector in which she is working and family setup . Fairly large proportion of teaching community is comprised of female teachers, which is one of the major service sectors chosen by women in the state. This paper highlighted problems faced by the female school teachers in CBSE School. For analysis, primary data have been collected and the same has been analysed.

Key Words: Breadwinner, Profession, Component, Problems & Responsibility

Introduction:

Women are playing a vital role in the economic and social development of the nations all over the world. Working women have a whole set of problems involving both family and professional lives. Women have to play their role as a wife, a mother and an earner. They have to manage their career while maintaining traditional roles. That means for working women it is two sets of overlapping responsibilities. Therefore, in addition to their traditional roles, professional roles seem to be one of the major sources of stress that working women have to face. Women are the pillar of society and play an important role in society, in all fields of life, without their participation no society can nurture properly. In most countries all teacher decisions are left to the teachers. The teachers are closest to their subjects and developments therein. They must make curriculum, teaching methods and grading decisions which are at heart of the education system. Due to some forces like spiritual customs and social traditions, women cannot freely participate in employment. These limitations are decreasing gradually to the normal position and this is becoming helpful in empowering women. Undoubtedly, without the active participation of women in national activities, the social, economic or political progress of a country will deteriorate and become stagnant. But ironically and tragically, women employees in general, are not taken very seriously by their superiors, colleagues, or society at large. Having a career poses challenges for women due to their family responsibilities. Traditionally Indian women had been home makers but in the recent decades, proper education and better awareness, in addition to the ever increasing cost of living has made them to go out and choose careers. Women have the responsibilities to effectively manage their multiple roles in domestic as well as professional lives. Men generally do not offer any help in the households work. This makes the life of working women extremely stressful.

Review of Literature:

Teaching is not only a noble profession, but also a demanding occupation where teachers need to maintain a high level of professional performance. They must accept personal responsibility for their own performance, growth and development. Therefore, teaching is considered one of the highest stress occupations, especially for the women who need to deal with both work and family.

Mitra (1997) analyses the causes and comes to some important conclusions: "Relationship between women and professions could be perceived as one of women in full-fledged professions, medicine, law, academics, etc and another in the semi-professions-like nursing, teaching, clerks etc."

Ornstein (1980) concluded that one of the major aspect of teacher's problems with inadequate salaries and lack of promotional opportunities. Although teachers' salaries are presently increasing as compared to past

but they are still fall far short of those of many other professional groups. Apart from this there is smoothing troublesome about a system where you hold teachers in the same position for 20 to 30 years without a promotion. Many are compelled to take second job after school time or during summer months or other vacation periods. He has maintained that salaries of administrative personal are typically high but much higher than the salaries of teachers and so teachers are tended that administration is more important function and lucrative then teaching.

Farber (1983) stated that in schools, teachers are likely feel to be distressed by the physical condition of their schools. Crumbling walls and ceilings graffiti inside and outside the school building, classrooms with peeling paints, fixtures without light bulbs, windows that was not open, and bathrooms absent or without privacy, asbestos problems, heating problems. These are some of the complaints and problems that teachers make often futilely to their principals, union representatives or any Government high ups. Poor working condition in schools that are form inadequate supplies to a shortage of desk, black boards and books etc. may wear down both teacher and students.

Barray. A Farber. (1991) crisis in education, jossey-bass publishers, San Francisco Oxford.

Statement of the Problem:

Major parts of Indian women are allowed to work still they face many problems in workplace and family. In spite of the outstanding performance, women teachers are not free from problems while achieve their goal. The basic problem of women teachers is that she women, this pertains to her responsibility towards family, society and work. This research is to find out problems faced by working teachers in CBSE schools in Erode District.

Scope of the Study:

The present study is confined to highlight the occupational problems of women teachers working in CBSE schools in Erode District. The study covers only the women teachers working in CBSE schools. The study deals with the socio-economic characteristics of women teachers.

Objectives of the Study:

The present study is undertaken with the following specific objectives:

- ✓ To find out the problems faced by Female school teachers in CBSE schools with special reference to Erode District.
- ✓ To offer suitable suggestions to overcome those problems.

Research Methodology:

This is an empirical study based on primary data. Convenient sampling technique has been adopted for collection of primary data. Required data have been collected from the selected 100 sample respondents. Due to non-response of the respondents to some questions, it is not possible to use the 07 interview schedule. Finally, information obtained from 93 respondents have been used for further analysis.

Data Collection:

The study uses both primary and secondary data. For the purpose of study, well structured questionnaire was used as an instrument to collect the data from the women teachers working in CBSE Schools of Erode district.

Primary Data:

Primary data was collected to get first hand information about a topic and for the purpose of analyzing information. The collection of data was done mainly through a survey with the help of a structured questionnaire.

Secondary Data:

Secondary data was collected through documentary research method. The secondary data is mainly related with theoretical aspects, emerging trends and various concepts for the study. Information has been obtained from various sources like Books, Journals and periodicals, Newspapers and magazines, Websites and so on.

Framework Analysis:

The present study has been undertaken to examine the problems of working women in schools with the help of statistical tool like Garrett’s Ranking Technique.

Table 1: Problems Faced By Working Women in CBSE Schools (Garret's Ranking Technique)

S.No	Problems	Rank	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII
		X	83	72	65	59	55	50	45	40
1	Working Environment	f	8	9	7	10	11	10	8	9
		fx	664	648	455	590	605	500	360	360
2	Job Freedom	f	10	7	9	12	8	7	9	8
		fx	830	504	585	708	440	350	405	320
3	Fees Charged for Transport	f	9	11	9	7	9	8	11	10
		fx	747	792	585	413	495	400	495	400
4	Institution Policies	f	10	10	12	8	9	8	8	9

		fx	830	720	780	472	495	400	360	360
5	Less or No Increment	f	10	11	9	10	9	9	8	11
		fx	830	792	585	590	495	450	360	440
6	Relationship with Students	f	9	9	9	9	8	11	10	9
		fx	747	648	585	531	440	550	450	360
7	Leave Facility	f	9	10	11	11	10	8	8	10
		fx	747	720	715	649	550	400	360	400
8	Time Convenient	f	8	8	9	7	11	11	10	9
		fx	664	576	585	413	605	550	450	360
9	Family Problems	f	9	7	10	11	9	11	10	9
		fx	747	504	650	649	495	550	450	360
10	Salary and Allowances	f	11	11	8	8	9	10	11	9
		fx	913	792	520	472	495	500	495	360
Total			93	93	93	93	93	93	93	93

S.No	Problems	Rank	IX	X	Total Score	Mean Score	Rank
		X	35	28			
1	Working Environment	f	11	10	93	52.12	IX
		fx	385	280	4847		
2	Job Freedom	f	12	11	93	52.37	VIII
		fx	420	308	4870		
3	Fees Charged for Transport	f	9	10	93	52.92	VI
		fx	315	280	4922		
4	Institution Policies	f	8	11	93	53.82	IV
		fx	280	308	5005		
5	Less or No Increment	f	7	9	93	54.18	III
		fx	245	252	5039		
6	Relationship with Students	f	10	9	93	52.83	VII
		fx	350	252	4913		
7	Leave Facility	f	8	8	93	54.25	II
		fx	280	224	5045		
8	Time Convenient	f	11	9	93	52.04	X
		fx	385	252	4840		
9	Family Problems	f	8	9	93	53.09	V
		fx	280	252	4937		
10	Salary and Allowances	f	9	7	93	54.39	I
		fx	315	196	5058		
Total			93	93			

Source: Interview schedule; X = Scale value f = Number of respondents; fx = Score

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1 shows that the main problem felt by the sample respondent is salary and allowances (highest mean score of 54.39) proves to be the most significant problem, this is followed by leave facility, less or no increment, institution policies, family problems, fees charged for transport, relationship with students, job freedom, working environment and time convenient.

Recommendations and Suggestions:

This study primarily aims at knowing the problems faced by female teachers. Based on the findings, the following suggestions are given to improve the level of job satisfaction of the teachers.

- ✓ In the present study, it is found that the most significant problem is salary and allowances. The school management should come forward to give reasonable salary for the teachers to cope with present cost of living.
- ✓ They should come forward to have a more healthy relationship with their teachers and they should provide better basic amenities such as casual leave and medical leave.
- ✓ The school managements should not give too much overload to the teachers and they should not compel the teachers to work beyond the working hours and on holidays.
- ✓ The managements should take adequate steps to provide a secured job to the teachers and they should be given enough rest for body and mind.
- ✓ The management of CBSE schools should revise the pay scales at regular intervals to motivate the teachers and also the government should come forward to fix and regulate the pay structures and other benefits. Hence it is suggested that proper steps taken by the Authority Concerned.

Conclusion:

On the basis of the findings, a suggestion has been offered if this suggestion has been seriously consider by the Authority Concerned, it is hope that still more number of teachers will come and join CBSE Schools. Moreover there is no proper policy of promotion for private sector teachers that also causes dissatisfaction to them. To avoid the problems of women teachers the management should give proper attention on salary, benefits and work load, job security and like; then only the employers of CBSE schools will be able to retain the teachers who are the valuable assets to their institutions.

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